

FLORETTE MORAND, A MISUNDERSTANDING POET? DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8025631**Annick Marie Belrose⁹**

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ABSTRACT

It's been a century since the women of Martinique and Guadeloupe have been writing. In 1924, three years after René Maran's renowned *Batoula*, Suzane Lacascade, from Guadeloupe, published in Paris the novel *Claire Solange, âme africaine* by the publisher Eugène Figuière. She received the Montyon Prize from the French Academy, and can be considered a pioneer of Négritude. Drasta Hoüel published the collection of prose poems *Les vies légères*, in 1916, and the novel *Cruautés et tendresses*, in 1925. Since then, the number of female writers has continued to increase. However, except for some authors such as: Maryse Condé, Simone Schwarz-Bart and Michèle Lacroisil whose novels have been the subject of several critical studies, the woman writer from the French Caribbean seems to suffer certain marginalization and remains forgotten by critics, although her production, in the context of the French Caribbean Literature, is of quality. When dealing with the poetesses specifically, it is clear that the erasure is even greater. This article aims to highlight the poetic work of Florette Morand (1926-2019) from Guadeloupe which, according to Naudillon (2002, p.69) is the one that most generated conflicts between the two most important criticisms dedicated to her.

Keywords: Literature. Literature. Francophone female poetry. Morand Florette. Guadeloupe.

The corpus of French-speaking Antillean literature is still not stable because its teaching is still marginalized, due to the lack of tradition and transmission in the French education system, but also because it is a literature that is still quite misunderstood, although it has acquired a well-recognized autonomy. Chancé (2008) argues that from the point of view of critical discourse, this corpus is quite atrophied, reduced, as a certain selection is observed, which is sometimes very severe in this corpus. This selection would be based on the notion of nation and territory, which leads to the exclusion of some authors from the colonial past, and in the absence of this criterion, there is a legitimation that:

It passes through sometimes subtle criteria of Antilleanness, that is, an authenticity marked by an emotional and cultural connection to the native country (which includes residing there) and by a stylistic originality that,

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however, must remain outside exoticism [. ..] thus, authors suspected of having imitated or followed metropolitan models were rejected. ¹⁰(CHANCE 2008, p.131)

We can cite as an example Toumson (1989, p.13) for whom Antillean literature in French is, above all, “a literature of cultural and racial awareness”, including both white and black writers, and which is born mainly in the beginning of the 20th century. For him, the emergence of this awareness took place in successive stages. Maignan-Claverie (2005), by choosing the strategy of the regularity of the Antillean discourse instead of the contents or the enunciative contexts, distinguishes a set of ancient representations that goes until the end of the 19th century, and that is characterized by “[...] its cultural allocentrism, by a constant reference to Europe [...] Antillean literature is an exotic and regionalist writing with variable specificities.” ¹¹(MAIGNAN-CLAVERIE, 2005, p.233), and another set of representations that begins in the 20th century with the emergence of Negritude.

Criticisms about the presentist character of this literature are being accompanied by others about its sexist bias, by privileging mostly male writers to the detriment of women.

It is in this context that we highlight here the poetic work of Florentine Adelaïde Morand or Florette MORAND, from Guadeloupe, which rarely appears in anthologies of French-speaking Antillean literature. Florette MORAND is an Afro-Antillean poet. He was born in Guadeloupe in 1926, in the city of *Morne à L'eau* and died in February 2019, aged 93, in Italy, which had become his second homeland, after his marriage in the 70s, to Count Aldo Capasso, her translator, but also a poet and literary critic, founder together with Lionello Fumi of Lyrical Realism in 1949. She lived in an important moment in the history of the French Antilles, which was the transition from a slave society, based on the plantation economy to the assimilation law of 1946. On that date he was 20 years old.

Morand was a teacher and a committed activist from an early age and has demonstrated her spirit of commitment on several occasions. For example, after the murder of African-American teenager Emmet Till, on August 28, 1955, in Money Mississippi, in the Mississippi Delta region, she expresses her indignation in a poem dedicated to him. In the early 1960s, she organized a press conference to denounce the arrest of Patrice Lumumba. In June 1962, she paid tribute in public after the crash of the plane in which the great poet and novelist from

¹⁰ Elle passe par des critères parfois subtils d'antillanité, c'est à dire d'une authenticité qui se marque par un attachement affectif et culturel au countrys natal (ce qui inclut d'y résider) et par une originalité esthétique, qui, toutefois, doit se garder de l'exotisme [...] Ainsi les auteurs soupçonné d'avoir imité, suivi les modèles métropolitains, ont-ils été rejetés.

¹¹[...] son allocentrisme culturel, par une constante référence à l'Europe [...] la littérature antillaise est portée vers l'écriture exotique et régionaliste, selon des spécificités variables.

Guadeloupe Albert Béville, alias Paul Niger, who was an anti-assimilationist, founding member of the Antillean-Guyanese Front for Autonomy along with with Glissant. The same returned to Guadeloupe fleeing the reprisals of the French authorities. Also on that same flight was Deputy Justin Catayée, from French Guiana, founder of the Guyanese Socialist Party. She dedicated the poem *Ma part de votre mal* to both of them. She was also at the side of the Basse-Terre prisoners after the May 1967 massacres in Guadeloupe and visited them despite the still simmering tensions. In 1957, Morand participated in the creation of ACRA (Académie Créole Antillaise) whose main objective was the defense of the creole language through the study of its origins, the fixation of its spelling. According to Chamoiseau and Confiant (1991, p.106), the ACRA was very similar to the Provençal Felibritge (Provençal literary movement started in the mid-nineteenth century to revitalize the Occitan language and culture headed by the poet Frédéric Mistral).

Her first poems were published in the magazine *Revue Guadeloupéenne* , a periodical that was published between 1945 and 1965 and in which she was a collaborator. This magazine brought together authors from all social and ethnic strata. One can find his poem *Dialogue avec la Ravine Espérance* in magazine n°15 of 1948. His three best-known collections of poems are: *Mon coeur est un oiseau des Îles - Poèmes*, a collection of 46 poems published in Paris in 1954, with a preface by Paul Fort, French poet and playwright. *Chanson de ma savane* . Collection of 77 poems published in 1958, with a preface by Pierre Mac Orlan (French novelist) from Academia Goncourt. *Feu de Brouse* published in Montreal in 1967. She is also the author of a collection of short stories and novels entitled *Biguines* from 1956. Many of her poems have been translated into Italian and German and she has received several literary prizes. In 1947, she won the competition of the Association of Students of Guadeloupe in Paris, for her telenovela *l'Ombre du Bambou* . He was awarded the French Prose Prize in 1949 by the *Académie des Jeux Floraux* de Guadalupe, which aimed to promote poetry in French and Creole. Laureate of the Auguste Capdeville prize for the collection *Chanson pour ma savane* in 1959, and the *Capuran* prize in 1968 for the collection *Feu de Brouse* , both French Academy awards. Even so, little has been written about her, although her poetry constitutes an important link in the construction of the literary history of Guadeloupe, in a time (between the two world wars) of political and cultural transformations and mutations of poetic sensibility. This period was, according to Toumson (1989, p.315) one of controversies where the antinomy between the aspiration to full French citizenship and the affirmation of the ethnocultural originality of the Antilles and Guyana fueled incessant polemics.

That said, Naudillon (2002) points out two relevant contributions with regard to the work of Florette Morand. That of Jack Corzani, French critic in *La littérature des Antilles et de la Guyane françaises, volume VI*, from 1978 and that of Roger Toumson, critic from Guadeloupe, in *La transgression des couleurs, Vol II*, from 1989. According to Naudillon (2002),

What draws attention when reading these pages is the great discrepancy in the critical reception of the poetess from Guadeloupe, one by the French critic, the other by a Martinican [...] for the first quite disdainful, for the second with a look more forgiving. On the other hand, what brings these two visions together is less the analysis of the poetic style than the ideological reach of the critical discourse when it comes to Florette Morand. ¹²(NAUDILLON, 2002, p.69)

To these two criticisms, we add the contribution of Eric Mansfield (2009). Both Corzani and Toumson (1989) associate Morand's work with literary regionalism. Corzani states that, "his work ignores ardent prophecies, it is only the reflection of a timid hope, that of the regionalists, frightened by the idea of rupture, anxious to reconcile, at the cost of some illusions, justice and fidelity." ¹³(CORZANI apud MANSFIELD, 2009, p.143). Toumson, in a more moderate way, points out that: "if the way of saying is borrowed, the way of seeing is not. The look is uncompromising. The issue of racial and social inequality is present from one collection to another. The memory of African origins is rediscovered." ¹⁴(TOUMSON, 1989, p.319). Mansfield (2009, p.143), in turn, after analyzing some of the author's poems, includes Morand in a subcategory, that of critical-regionalism. In its classification, it is worth noting the difference between the titles attributed by him when analyzing other poems in the same category and from the same period written by men. For Morand, there is the title *Florette Morand, l'inconsolée* (the inconsolable), an adjective associated with loss, pain, crying, denoting a certain inferiority, thus reducing the scope of the author's poetry. Whereas, for male poets the titles are quite different. There is, for example: Louis Porto (1921), *Une contribution du régionalisme Antillais à la culture française*. ¹⁵Ancelot Bellaire (1913), *Une littérature teintée*

¹²Ce qui frappe à la lecture de ces pages c'est le grand écart dans la réception critique de la poétesse guadeloupéenne, l'une par un critique de France, l'autre par un Martiniquais, pour le premier assez méprisant, pour le second avec un regard plus indulgent. In revenge, ce qui rassemble ces deux regards c'est moins l'analyse du style poétique que la portée idéologique du discours critique dès qu'il s'agit de Florette Morand.

¹³Son oeuvre ignore les prophéties enflammées, elle n'est que le reflet d'une timide espérance, celle des régionalistes effrayés à l'idée d'une rupture, désireux de concilier, au prix peut-être de quelques illusions, la justice et la loyauté.

¹⁴Si la manière de dire est empruntée, la manière de voir ne l'est pas. Le regard est sans complaisance. La question relative à l'iniquité raciale et à l'inégalité sociale est présente d'un recueil à l'autre. La mémoire des origines africaines est retrouvée.

¹⁵A contribution of Antillean regionalism to French culture

de régionalisme comme des épices ajoutées à des mets métropolitains ¹⁶et Serge Vipart, *Un poète soucieux de la protection de l'environnement* ¹⁷, (MANSFIELD, 2009, p.146-148) clearly showing the value of this masculine poetry.

The regionalist character of Morand's poetry does not justify its exclusion from the literary scene of the French Antilles, since, as Toumson (2003) rightly states, at that time, “The first black intellectuals did not have an autonomous discursive structure. Remaining close to their origins, they adhered to the ideals of the mulatto intelligentsia, which endeavored to justify its attachment to France in the name of republican principles. It was she who [...] made the Schoelcherian ideological myth prevail” ¹⁸(TOUMSON, 2003, p.108).

It is believed, therefore, that Morand's work deserves a different look given the political and cultural context of the time. Chery (2022, p.60-61) emphasizes the need to reread Morand's poetry, as it is much richer than a superficial reading provides. She classifies Morand's three collections as milestones of a writing experience, of progress in its own way. *Mon cœur est un oiseau des Îles – Poèmes* would constitute an entry in poetry. *Chanson pour ma Savane* would privilege a relationship with music, with lighter themes with descriptions marked by personal reflections and *Feu de Brousse* would be a work of maturity.

Naudillon (2002, p.76), when analyzing this latest collection *Feu de Brousse*, highlights that the poetic form adopted by Morand is extremely varied. The collection alternates poems in free verse, poetic prose, octosyllable or alexandrine poems or composed of odd verses (five syllables). She classifies them into several categories: the poems of the self (22); American poems (21), among which are poems about Guadeloupe, Guyana, about the natives of Guyana, about Brazil and the Amazon (7), about Harlem and jazz, an African poem that gives the title to the collection, and another dedicated to the city of Hamburg, after the floods of 1962. According to the same, there is a contrast between the poems of the self and the American poems, “[...] the first full of a universe ordered as a French garden, in which each plant would grow anarchically and the seconds more tormented. But all the poems share the same obsession: to escape, to another place” ¹⁹. (NAUDILLON, 2002, p.82). In general, according to the author, “[...] the poetic universe constructed by Florette Morand is characterized by obsession, tremor,

¹⁶A literature tinged with regionalism like spices added to metropolitan delicacies.

¹⁷A poet concerned with protecting the environment

¹⁸Les premiers intellectuels noirs ne disposent pas d'une structure discursive autonome. Restant proches de leurs origines, ils sont gagnés aux idéaux de l'intelligentsia mulâtre, laquelle s'appliquait à justifier son attachement à la France au nom des principes républicains. C'est elle qui, [...] a fait prévaloir le mythe idéologique schoelcherien.

¹⁹[...] les premiers, tous emplis d'un univers ordonné comme un jardin à la française, mais dont chaque plante pousserait de façon anarchique, les seconds plus tourmentés. Mais tous partagent la même hantise: la fuite, l'Ailleurs.

fear and the desire to flee from an oppression that is sometimes defined (such as hunger, misery), sometimes suggested (dangerousness/The dangers of nature)”²⁰. (NAUDILLON, 2002, p.83).

In conclusion, we believe that beyond political loyalty or ideological convictions, the censorship imposed on Morand's work for the lack of responsibility or commitment to the dominated context of the French West Indies no longer applies. Morand's work deserves attention and space in Antillean literature in French for having contributed to the development of self-consciousness in the Antillean-Guyanese community mentioned by Toumson (1989).

REFERENCES

- CHANCE.D. Le corpus de la littérature des Antilles françaises: une peau de chagrin . *In* DEBALINE.D. ABDELKADER.Y. CHANCE.D. Théories et transmissions des littératures francophones. Pessac: Presses Universitaire de Bordeaux-PUB, 2008. Available at: <https://books.openedition.org/pub/42664>. Accessed on 10/02/2022.
- CHERY.C. Revoila Florette Morand. *C'smart* Guadeloupe n°19, 2022, p.60-61. Available at <https://csmart.ewag.fr/>. Accessed on 10/05/2022.
- MAIGNAN-CLAVERIE.C. Le métissage dans la littérature des Antilles françaises. Le complexe d'Ariel. Paris: Karthala, 2005.
- MANSFIELD.E. La symbolique du regard-regardants et regardés dans la poésie d'expression française. Martinique, Guadeloupe, Guyane 1945-1982. Paris: Publibook, 2009.
- NAUDILLON.F. Florette Morand. *In* GUBIN.E. Poetry. Sextant. Revue du groupe interdisciplinaire d'études sur les femmes de l'Université Libre de Bruxelles. Vol.17-18, 2002. Available at: http://digistore.bib.ulb.ac.be/2017/a082_2002_017-018_f.pdf. Accessed on 9/1/2022.
- TOUMSON.R. La transgression des couleurs. Littératures et langages des Antilles, XVIII^{and}, XIX^{and}, XX^{and} siècles, Tome II. Paris: Editions Caribbean, 1989.
- TOUMSON.R. Les littératures caribéennes francophones. Problèmes et perspectives. In: Cahiers de l'Association internationale des études françaises, 2003, n°55. pp. 103-121. Available at https://www.persee.fr/doc/caief_0571-5865_2003_num_55_1_1488. Accessed 04/21/2018.

²⁰[...] l'univers poétique que construit Florette Morand se caractérise par la hantise, le tremblement, la peur et la volonté de fuir une oppression tantôt définie (Oa faim, la misère), tantôt suggérée (la dangerosité de la nature).